

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MEDICAL PEDAGOGY

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Abstract. *Artificial intelligence computer systems are widely used in the medical sciences. Common applications include diagnosing patients, discovering and developing drugs, improving communication between doctors and patients, transcribing medical documents such as prescriptions, and treating patients remotely. While computer systems often perform tasks more efficiently than humans, recently state-of-the-art computer algorithms have achieved accuracy comparable to human experts in the field of medical sciences. Artificial intelligence is widely used in medicine to improve clinical diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment. Below are some of the benefits of artificial intelligence in various fields of medicine.*

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, genomics, biotechnology, telemedicine, robotics, automation, nanotechnology, the future of AI in medical sciences, medical education, modern medicine, medical pedagogy.*

INTRODUCTION:

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a new field of research that emerged in the mid-20th century. It is a technology that primarily uses computer systems to simulate human thought processes. AI is primarily associated with computer science, but it also encompasses languages, psychology, philosophy, mathematics, and other fields. Since the invention of AI in 1955, its applications have grown in a rapidly changing digital ecosystem, where public demands from social media, industry leaders, and physicians are increasing. AI has addressed a variety of educational problems over the past decade, including language processing, reasoning, planning, and cognitive modeling. A first-of-its-kind Web of Science search for AI in medical education revealed a growing interest in the topic. The increase in the total number of publications and the number of citations to articles over the past two decades indicates the recent growth in the use of AI in research and development in medical education. It can be used in medical education in the following ways: virtual inquiry system, medical distance learning and management, and recording educational videos in medical schools.

Medical education is a lifelong learning process that continues from undergraduate to postgraduate and specialty training and beyond. This also applies to various health professionals, including doctors, nurses, and other allied health professionals. Therefore, it is crucial to recognize that in this era of rapidly evolving technology, new works need to be built on existing materials to advance the topic of AI in medical education.

AI can enhance the value of non-analytical humanistic aspects of medicine. Among many opportunities, a health professional must be able to abstract and understand information in making medical judgments in an era where medical knowledge is growing exponentially. The efforts of doctors to understand digital data will be reduced by artificial intelligence, which will improve their diagnostic and problem-solving capabilities.

Digital learners are different from past generations. They are growing up in a digital world and value social connections. This generation of learners prefers to work in groups and share

details of their work with their peers using a variety of software applications. They value positive feedback on their achievements and need one-on-one intellectual support. Teachers need to discover and use appropriate teaching tactics to capture and engage students. For example, the Institute of Medicine (USA) held a multidisciplinary summit to integrate core competencies into health professional education and proposed a mix of approaches that included monitoring processes, learning environments, research, public reporting, and leadership. The educational mission “Training Tomorrow’s Physicians” outlined the challenges facing health care providers, accrediting agencies, and other comparable institutions, as well as public policy. In a highly connected world, medical education must evolve to meet changing healthcare scenarios, including digitalization and a new generation of healthcare students. Curriculum design and analysis, learning, and evaluation are areas where AI can be used in medical education. AI can minimize the time it takes to review different curricula, solve multi-dimensional problems, improve classification accuracy, and show the relationship between parameters in curriculum evaluation. For example, AI can assess the “curriculum effectiveness” and the “overall happiness” of medical students with a course curriculum, which is crucial in training future doctors. In the learning process, AI can help students receive flexible and personalized learning content that is improved with student feedback, allowing students to identify knowledge gaps and respond appropriately. Additionally, artificial intelligence makes the assessment process more accurate, faster, and more cost-effective, and effectively provides detailed, personalized feedback.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY:

The main directions of modern medicine today are the development of artificial intelligence and data analysis, which provide highly effective diagnosis and treatment in medicine. Artificial intelligence algorithms help in reading clinical data, making diagnoses, and planning treatment. Genomics holds the potential to provide personalized treatment based on genetic characteristics. Biotechnology plays an important role in creating high-speed and effective drugs, vaccines, and therapeutic models. Developments in the field of medicine on the Internet (telemedicine) provide faster and simpler exchange of ideas for the population. Remote consultations, medical care, and information exchange can be facilitated and accelerated. Nanotechnology is making huge changes at the molecular level in the creation of medicines. This will further improve the availability and direct quality of medicines. Robotics and automation in medicine are leading to changes in practices and treatment processes. These technologies help improve processes and reduce the number of errors. All of these areas form the basis of modern medicine and are aimed at providing highly effective, integrative approaches to healthcare.

Clinical diagnosis and diagnostic assistance. Artificial intelligence is making diagnoses based on clinical images and data. For example, radiological images, tomography results, and MRI scans are analyzed by algorithms based on the data provided.

Data analytics: Artificial intelligence performs data analysis in medicine based on clinical information, laboratory results, unchanging historical data, and other sources. This improves the analysis, prognosis, and treatment plans of diseases. **Personalization and prognostics:** Artificial intelligence helps in creating personalized treatment plans for each individual. Based on genomics and clinical data, artificial intelligence collects information relevant to the personality and shapes the treatment.

Robotics and automation: In medicine, robots and automated devices are used in clinical operations and treatment processes. Artificial intelligence also plays an important role in

optimizing clinical processes for robots. Artificial intelligence improves consultations in telemedicine. It provides the ability to exchange and display information with specialists in other regions or remote locations. The application of artificial intelligence in medicine makes medicine more efficient, achieves better results, and helps create breakthrough technologies in the fight against diseases. It helps in analyzing clinical images and diagnostics, radiological images (such as X-rays, MRIs, and CT scans) and identifying diseases. This speeds up radiological diagnosis in medicine and allows for more accurate diagnoses.

DISCUSSION:

Another area of application of artificial intelligence in education is chatbots and virtual assistants. They can provide students with information about courses, lesson schedules, and answer questions about course materials and assignments. This allows students to get quick answers to their questions and receive additional support in the learning process. AI systems can also be used to automatically check assignments and tests. They can analyze student answers and assess their accuracy and quality. This saves the teacher time and provides an objective assessment of the student's work. Some higher education institutions are also using AI systems to detect plagiarism. They can compare student work with databases of information sources to identify work that is not of the authors. This helps ensure honesty and academic ethics. Thus, the use of artificial intelligence systems in the modern organization of educational activities in higher education institutions allows to improve the educational process, adapt it to the individual needs of students and increase its efficiency. In modern educational practice, attention is paid to providing significant funds for the development of AI technologies and their use in teaching. Today, the digital transformation of the educational environment around the world implies the fundamental presence and implementation of AI. However, the rapid development of artificial intelligence technologies in higher education is accompanied by great complexity and many risks, requiring scientific solutions to constantly emerging problems associated with the use of such technologies. The use of artificial intelligence (AI) systems in the modern organization of educational activities in higher education institutions is becoming an increasingly common practice. AI is an innovative technology that can significantly improve student learning and support, as well as increase the efficiency of teachers and administrations of educational institutions. One of the main areas of application of artificial intelligence in education is the automation and personalization of learning. With the help of AI, you can create individual educational programs and manage the learning process, taking into account the needs, abilities and speed of learning of the material of each student. AI can analyze data on students' learning activities, such as assignment and test results, and suggest appropriate materials and teaching methods. Another example of the use of artificial intelligence in education is the automation of reviewing and grading of educational works and tests. With the help of an AI system, it is possible to develop algorithms for checking and grading, which will reduce the time spent by teachers on this work and provide objective and uniform assessment criteria. AI can also be used to analyze data and predict learning outcomes. Predictive models based on AI can analyze large amounts of data about the learning process, academic performance and other factors to predict potential problems or success of students. This helps to quickly identify students who need additional support and take steps to improve them. AI can also be used to design and develop new technological tools and teaching methodologies. For example, AI-based virtual assistants can help students find information, solve problems, or conduct research. AI can also be used to create learning environments, such as virtual reality, that simulate real-life

situations and allow for more hands-on learning. However, despite the many benefits and prospects of using AI in education, there are also some challenges and issues. It is important to develop reliable AI systems that ensure data security and student privacy. It is also necessary to provide education and training for teachers and administrators to work with AI and understand its capabilities and limitations. In general, the use of artificial intelligence systems in the modern organization of educational activities in higher education institutions can significantly improve the educational process, student support, and the effectiveness of teachers and administrators. However, AI must be carefully planned and implemented, taking into account the needs and context of the organization and teaching. AI technologies are penetrating all aspects of human life, including education. Their full implementation, of course, requires a scientific and theoretical understanding of the ongoing processes

RESULTS:

The future of medical education will largely be powered by AI-based technologies, helping teachers better understand their students and helping each student learn according to their own learning style, and allowing educational institutions to focus more on teaching communication, ethics, and morality. While the risk of bias remains in these AI-based educational systems, more research will help clarify this issue to a greater extent. The use of AI robots in surgery is still in its infancy. Since it involves minimizing the risk to the patient's life and saving financial resources, progress in this area is expected to be gradual. These surgical procedures will become commonplace as technology and cost increase, and medical schools that do not provide robotic surgery will quickly fall behind. On the one hand, medical education must incorporate AI to ultimately remain relevant. However, it is equally important to properly train "AI systems". Finally, educating future doctors about AI technology and its ethical issues is crucial to creating a healthcare system that is different from today's medicine.

CONCLUSION:

The aim of this article was to present the implications of AI in medical education over the past two decades, its current scenario and future applications. Thus, high-quality data that met the research objectives were included. In addition, a comprehensive review of the articles available in reputable databases such as PubMed, ResearchGate, PubMed Central, Web of Science and Google Scholar was conducted to review the literature. The main index words or phrases used in the literature search were artificial intelligence, healthcare and AI, artificial intelligence and medical education, artificial intelligence in medical science, doctors and artificial intelligence, new dimensions in medical education, medical doctors, postgraduate courses and AI.

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